

DDT were dusted at 37.5 and 12.5 kg/ha.

Live insects were collected with 5 sweeps of a net at scattered spots in each

plot before and 3 and 15 days after application.

All insecticides gave significant control of WBPH at 3 days, then effective-

ness decreased (see table). MIPC and carbaryl gave excellent control at 3 days. Evidently, insecticide application should be repeated every 10-15 days. ■

Control of rice mites

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A trial in 1980 kuruvai season evaluated insecticides for controlling the rice mite *Oligonychus oryzae* (Hirst). A severe infestation on rice variety ADT36 was utilized. Insecticides monocrotophos (Nuvacron), methyl demeton (Metasystox), phosalone (Zolone), phosphamidon (Dimecron), and endosulfan

Effect of insecticides on rice mite density at Tamil Nadu, India.

Insecticide	Formulation	Dosage (kg a.i./ha)	Mite density ^a (no./10cm ² leaf area)	Pest reduction (%)
Monocrotophos	40 EC	0.25	Sa	90
Methyl demeton	25 EC	0.16	15 c	68
Phosalone	35 EC	0.22	22 d	55
Phosphamidon	100 EC	0.63	10 b	78
Endosulfan	35 EC	0.22	10 b	79
Control	-	-	48 e	-

^a Means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at 0.05% level.

(Corosulfan) were sprayed at 625 liters/ha on 20-m² plots. Mite density was observed, 72 hours after treatment, on 1-cm² leaf areas or 10 leaves

selected randomly from 10 hills/plot.

All insecticides reduced mite density; monocrotophos was most effective (see table). ■

Rice gall midge and its parasites

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The damage caused by the gall midge *Orseolia oryzae* in Madhya Pradesh and adjoining states is influenced by parasites. A trial with the highly susceptible variety TN1 during the 1978 wet season continued on stubble during the dry season. Healthy and parasitized gall midges were recorded weekly on tillers from early September (36th calendar week) 1978 to early December (49th calendar week) and on stubble from mid-January (3d calendar week) 1979 to early March (9th calendar week).

Gall midge infestation started the first week of September, gradually reaching a maximum in the second week of

Incidence of healthy and parasitized gall midge in Raipur, M.P., India, 1978-79

November (see figure). Parasitization started the fourth week of September and reached its highest level the last week of November. In stubble, the gall

midge population was 3.4-8.4% and the parasite population was 8.5-15.8%.

The data show the role of parasites in minimizing pest pressure. ■

Evaluation of insecticides for toxicity to brown planthopper eggs and nymphs

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Fourteen insecticides were tested for knockdown effect and persistent toxicity against brown planthopper (BPH) *Nilaparvata lugens* (Stal) nymphs. The insecticides were sprayed on 40-day-old TN1 plants. Insects were caged at regular intervals.

Fenvalerate, cypermethrin, and carbosulfan as 0.05% sprays exhibited quick knockdown effects and persistent

toxicity. However, fenvalerate and cypermethrin were less persistent at normally recommended concentrations (0.01 and 0.005%). BPMC showed good knockdown effect but had less persistent toxicity. Isofenphos (EC and WP), bendiocarb, endosulfan, phenthoate, acephate, MIPC, UC51762, phosmet, and phoxim were less toxic.

Contact studies with the Potters